

Map 40. The public
space Network

Map 1.1 THESSALONIKI 1-2
AXIAL MAP

Map 1-2. THESSALY 3
AXIAL MAP

Map 2. THESSCITY 1-2
INTEGRATION MAP

— 5% most integrated lines
(Integration core)

- - - 50% most segregated lines

Map 3. THESSCITY 3
INTEGRATION MAP
5% most integrated
lines
50% most segregated
lines

Map 4. THESETHIN
INTEGRATION MAP

— 5% most integrated lines
— 50% most segregated lines

Map 5.a. THESSCITY 1-2.
 Integration Core of the market
 area. (JMAR 1890)

Map 5. THESSCITY 1-2.
 INTEGRATION MAP OF CITY
 QUARTERS (TQs)
 5% most integrated lines
 60% most segregated lines

Map 6. THESSUP 1-2
INTEGRATION MAP
5% most integrated lines
(Integration core)
50% most segregated lines

Map 7. THESSCITY 1-2
CONTROL VALUES
10 % higher C.V.

Map 8. THESSCITY 1-2
INTELLIGIBILITY VALUES

Map 9 a. MARKET AREA (TMAP 1-2)
CONTROL VALUES
10% highest C.V.

Map 9. THESSALY 1-2-3
CONTROL VALUES OF
ETHNOQUARTERS
10% higher C.V.

Map 10 . THESSALY 1-2
INTELLIGIBILITY VALUES OF
ETHNOQUARTERS

Map 11. THESSUP 1-2
CONTROL VALUES
10% highest C.V.

Map 12 • THESSUP 1-2
INTELLIGIBILITY VALUES

Map 13. THEBES CITY 1-2
CONTROL VALUES OF
CITY-QUARTERS (TQs)
10% highest C.V.

- TQs

Map 14. THESSALY 3
CONTROL VALUES
10% highest C.V.

Map 16 . THESSALY 3
INTELLIGIBILITY VALUES

Map 16. THESSCITY 1-2
CHOICE VALUES
10% highest CH.V.

Map 17 • THESSALY 1-2
MOVEMENT INTERFACE

Map 18.a. MARKET AREA (TMAR)
CHOICE VALUES

Map 18. THESSALY 1-2
CHOICE VALUES OF ETHNO-
QUARTERS
10% highest CH.V.

Map 19 • THESSALY 1-2
MOVEMENT INTERFACE OF
ETHNOQUARTERS

Map 20 . THESSUP 1-2
CHOICE VALUES
10 % highest CH.V.

Map 21 , THESSUP 1-2
MOVEMENT INTERFACE

Map 22 . THESSCITY 1-2
CHOICE VALUES OF CITY-
QUARTERS (TQs)
10% highest CH.V.

Map 23 . THESSCITY 3
CHOICE VALUES
10% highest CH.V

Map 24. THESSALY 3
CHOICE VALUES OF CITY-
QUARTERS (70s)
10% highest CH.V.

Map 25 . THE SCITY 3
MOVEMENT INTERFACE

Map 26. THESSCITY 4
AXIAL MAP

Map 27. THESSICITY 4
INTEGRATION MAP

— 5% most integrated lines (integration core)
 ... 50% most segregated lines

Map 28. THESSALY 4.
INTEGRATION MAP OF CITY-QUARTERS (TQs)

— 5% most integrated lines (Tq core)

- - - City integration core

Map 29 • THESSUP 4

INTEGRATION MAP

5% most integrated lines
(Integration Core)

50% most segregated lines
City Integration core

Map 30. THESSALY 4
CONTROL VALUES
10% highest C.V.

map- 31 • THESSALY 4
INTELLIGIBILITY VALUES

Map 32 . THESSUP 4
CONTROL VALUES
10% highest C.V.